

Appendix A – Average training and validation loss across setups

Figure A1. Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-1 (ITS4SDC).

Figure A2. Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-2 (ITS4SDC).

Figure A3. Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-5 (ITS4SDC).

Figure A4. Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-6 (ITS4SDC).

Appendix B – Confusion matrices across setups

Figure B1. Confusion matrices across setups